

A STUDY ON TEACHERS OPINION TOWARDS E-LEARNING IN UDHAM SINGH NAGAR DISTRICT OF UTTARAKHAND

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Abstract:

Important changes have been seen in the field of education due to the technological advancements. E-learning is an upcoming method that used technology to assist student learning. It is one of the tools that has emerged from information technology and has been integrated in many universities. A teacher is the most crucial part for delivery through e-learning. The present study is survey research where it aims to study the opinion of teachers towards e-learning in general and to study the opinion of male and female teachers and government and private teachers in particular. Opinion towards e-learning scale self-developed by investigator was employed in the current study. For this purpose, 200 samples were collected from government and private colleges from Udham Singh Nagar district of Uttarakhand. Collected data were organized and tabulated on the basis of scores and used Mean, Standard deviation and t-test for analyzing collected data. The results further indicated no significant gender difference teacher's opinion towards e-learning and also there exists no significant difference between government and private teachers in their opinion toward e-learning.

Keywords: E- learning, Opinion, Opinion towards e-learning, Teachers

Introduction:

Learning is a purposeful and planned activity that results in observable and lasting changes in behaviour through experience, study, and instruction. Traditionally, Indian classrooms involved face-to-face interaction between teachers and students, but advancements in computer technology and the Internet have transformed this system, giving rise to e-learning. E-learning refers to teaching and learning conducted through electronic technologies, where teachers and learners may be geographically or temporally separated but connected via the Internet. It offers flexibility, accessibility, and cost-effectiveness, allowing learners to access educational content anytime and anywhere. In India and worldwide, e-learning is emerging as a major educational innovation, creating new opportunities for both teachers and learners. It supports a learner-centered approach, enhances performance, and promotes lifelong learning. Higher education institutions increasingly provide online resources such as lecture notes and study materials, thereby improving study flexibility. Organizations like UGC, NCERT, and NCTE actively encourage the development of e-learning infrastructure and quality enhancement in higher education.

E-learning has emerged as the newest trend in the contemporary society. Better opportunities for teaching and learning are offered by e-learning to both teachers and students. E-learning is basically the delivery of education via digital technologies that are networked and computer enabled. These

technologies include computers, intranets, satellite television, CD-ROMs, computers, internet, and audio and video sources. Using information and communication technologies, e-learning is a novel idea in education that improves and promotes learning by distributing digital content and creating a learner-centered environment for both teachers and students. This education could take the form of fully online classes or email exchanges between instructors and students. Thus, it is a changing trend in the field of education.

Literature Review:

Kumar and Kumar (2011) carried out a study to know the attitude of teachers of Higher Education towards e-learning. The findings of this study revealed that the teachers had a favourable attitude towards e-learning. The teachers who were familiar with computers and information and communication technology differ in their attitude towards e-learning when compared to the teachers who were not familiar with technology.

Rozinah and Merza (2012) in their research revealed that there is no significant difference in the teacher candidates' attitudes and self-efficacy toward e-learning on the basis of gender and age group

Suri & Sharma (2016) conducted study on "Investigation of Teacher's Attitude towards e-learning". Study conducted among 85 teachers from six major faculties of Panjab University, Chandigarh, reveals an overall favorable attitude toward e-learning. The findings indicate that teachers support the integration of e-learning with traditional teaching methods, highlighting a positive inclination toward blended learning. Additionally, the study reports no significant gender differences in teachers' attitudes toward computers and e-learning. As an exploratory investigation of teachers' initial perceptions at the university level, the study provides a useful foundation for further research and offers valuable insights for designing and implementing effective e-learning platforms in higher education.

Farizi, A. (2018) conducted study on the investigation of lecturer's attitude towards e - learning according to demographic variables. The study's results revealed that there is not a significant difference between male and female lectures perspectives about the attitudes towards e – learning that affect its implementation, with female lecturers' attitudes being more common than male lecturers'.

Kaur Gagandeep (2019) conducted a study on "Attitude towards E-learning among Rural and Urban School Teachers in Relation to their Technostress" The main findings of the study are: 1 Rural school teachers significantly score higher than urban school teachers with respect to ease of e-learning, e-learning confidence and total attitude towards e-learning. 2 Rural school teachers score little higher than urban school teachers on e –learning interest and usefulness of e-learning. 3 Most of the rural as well as urban school teachers have medium level of techno stress. 4 Techno stress has weak but positive relationship with usefulness of e-learning. With all other dimensions the relation is very weak.

Jena Anshuman (2023) carried out a study on "A study on teachers' attitude towards e-learning". The study examined the attitudes of 64 secondary school teachers from the Cuttack district toward

e-learning with respect to gender, locale, and type of school. The findings revealed that the majority of teachers (71.9%) demonstrated a moderate level of attitude toward e-learning. No significant difference was observed based on gender. However, teachers from urban areas exhibited a more favorable attitude toward e-learning compared to their rural counterparts. Additionally, a significant difference was found between government and non-government school teachers, with government secondary school teachers showing a more positive attitude toward e-learning.

Need and Significance of the Study:

With the rapid integration of digital technologies in education, e-learning has become an essential component of teaching–learning processes. Understanding teachers’ opinions toward e-learning is crucial, as teachers play a central role in the successful adoption and implementation of digital instructional practices. The growing adoption of e-learning in higher education has transformed traditional teaching practices, making technology integration essential for effective instruction. College teachers play a pivotal role in the successful implementation of e-learning, as their opinions, attitudes, and readiness directly influence its acceptance and use in the classroom. In the Udham Singh Nagar district, where colleges differ in terms of resources, technological infrastructure, and exposure to digital teaching tools, it is important to examine college teachers’ opinions toward e-learning. Such a study is needed to understand their level of awareness, acceptance, and challenges faced while adopting e-learning in higher education institutions. The significance of this study lies in its potential to provide empirical evidence that can guide academic administrators, policymakers, and curriculum planners in strengthening e-learning initiatives at the college level. The findings may help identify gaps in digital skills, training requirements, and infrastructural support, enabling institutions to plan targeted professional development programs for teachers. Furthermore, the study can contribute to regional and national research on e-learning by offering district-specific insights, thereby supporting the effective and sustainable integration of e-learning in higher education.

Statement of the Problem:

A Study on Teachers Opinion Towards E-Learning in Udham Singh Nagar District of Uttarakhand

Objectives of the Study:

The following are the objectives of this study:

1. To find out the significant difference between the opinion of Teachers towards e-learning with respect to their gender.
2. To find out the significant difference between the opinion of Teachers towards e-learning with respect to type of Educational Institutions in which they are teaching i.e., Government or Private Institutions.

Hypotheses of the Study:

1. The following are the hypotheses of this study:

2. Male Teachers and female teachers do not differ in their Opinion toward E-Learning. The two variables namely Types of Educational Institution (government and private) and Opinion towards E-Learning are not associated with one another in case of the Teachers.

Research Methodology:

- **Selection of Research Method:** The present study tries to explore the opinion of teachers towards e-learning; hence it studies the present phenomena. Thus, the Descriptive survey method is applied in this study.
- **Population and Sample:** The population for this study comprises all teachers teaching in higher education institutions, including both government and private colleges located in Udham Singh Nagar district of Uttarakhand, affiliated with Kumaun University, Nainital. Out of total colleges (Government and Private), ten colleges are selected as a sample out of which 5 colleges are government and 5 colleges are privately managed. From ten colleges 200 teachers, 100 from government colleges and 100 from private colleges are selected by applying the random sampling technique.

Tool Used: In order to know the opinion of the teachers towards e-learning, an opinion scale was developed and standardized by the investigator based on an extensive review of relevant literature and discussions with teachers. An initial pool of 94 opinion statements was prepared. These items were subjected to content validation by eight experts from the field of teacher education, who evaluated them for clarity of language, structural adequacy, relevance, and redundancy. Based on their suggestions, irrelevant items were removed and some statements were modified. As a result, 69 items were retained for further testing.

The refined scale was administered to a sample of 50 teachers from four colleges as part of a pilot study to examine the suitability of the items. The reliability of the tool was assessed using Cronbach’s alpha to determine internal consistency. The analysis, carried out using SPSS, yielded a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.940, indicating excellent reliability. During this process, 12 items with low item–total correlations were eliminated. The final scale consisted of 57 items, all contributing positively to the reliability of the instrument. Thus, the finalized Opinion towards E-learning Scale was found to be highly reliable for data collection.

a) **Statistical Techniques:** For analysis of raw data, z-score, descriptive statistics, and t-tests are used in this study. The bar graph is also applied to show the level of attitude of higher secondary school students towards e-learning.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The collected data are analyzed and interpreted objective-wise in the following manner:

Hypothesis 1: Male Teachers and female teachers do not differ in their Opinion toward E-Learning.

Table No. 4.1: Showing mean, standard deviation and t-value of significant difference between opinion of male and female teachers towards e-learning.

Pair of	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Significance
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Comparison						at 0.05 level
Male Teachers	100	144.34	14.11	-1.261	198	Not Significant
Female Teachers	100	146.85	14.03			

Interpretation:

The above table shows significance difference between opinion of male and female teachers towards e-learning. It shows the mean of Male teachers is 144.34 and of Female teachers is 146.85 and Standard Deviation of Male teachers is 14.11 and of female teachers is 14.03. The calculate t-value is -1.261 at 198 degrees of freedom, indicating a no significant difference between opinion of male and female teachers towards e-learning. This means that male and female teachers have almost similar opinion toward e-learning.

Hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

Graph No. 1: Showing mean and standard deviation of Male and Female Teachers towards e-learning.

Hypothesis 2: The two variables namely Types of Educational Institution (government and private) and Opinion towards E-Learning are not associated with one another in case of the Teachers.

Table No. 4.1: Showing mean, standard deviation and t-value of significant difference between opinion of Government and Private teachers towards e-learning.

Pair of Comparison	N	Mean	SD	t-value	df	Significance at 0.05 level
Government	100	144.83	15.38	-.767	198	Not Significant

Private	100	146.36	12.71			
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Interpretation:

The above table shows significance difference between opinion of Government and Private teachers towards e-learning. It shows the mean of Government teachers is 144.83 and of Private teachers is 146.36 and Standard Deviation of Government teachers is 15.38 and of Private teachers is 12.71. The calculate t-value is .767 at 198 degrees of freedom, indicating a no significant difference between opinion of Government and Private teachers towards e-learning.

Graph No. 4.1: Showing mean and standard deviation of Government and Private teachers towards e-learning.

Findings of the Study:

After analysis and interpretation of collected data, the following findings emerged in the present research study.

1.The analysis reveals that there is no significant difference between the opinions of male and female teachers toward e-learning. Although female teachers (Mean = 146.85, SD = 14.03) have a slightly higher mean score than male teachers (Mean = 144.34, SD = 14.11), the calculated *t*-value (-1.261) at 198 degrees of freedom is not statistically significant. This indicates that both male and female teachers hold almost similar opinions toward e-learning.

2.The findings also show that there is no significant difference between the opinions of government and private teachers toward e-learning. While private teachers (Mean = 146.36, SD = 12.71) exhibit a marginally higher mean score compared to government teachers (Mean = 144.83, SD = 15.38), the calculated *t*-value (.767) at 198 degrees of freedom is not significant. This suggests that teachers from both government and private institutions have comparable opinions toward e-learning.

Implications of the Study:

The findings of the present study have important educational implications for teachers, administrators, curriculum planners, and policymakers:

•Uniform acceptance of e-learning: Since no significant differences were found between male and female teachers, and between government and private teachers, it implies that e-learning is uniformly accepted across different categories of teachers. Training and implementation strategies for e-learning can therefore be designed without gender- or institution-specific differentiation.

•Policy formulation and planning: Educational planners and policymakers can formulate common e-learning policies and programs applicable to both government and private institutions. The similarity in opinions suggests that large-scale adoption of e-learning initiatives is feasible across institutions.

Conclusion of the Study: The present study was conducted to examine teachers' opinions toward e-learning with respect to gender and type of institution. The analysis of data revealed that there is no statistically significant difference between the opinions of male and female teachers toward e-learning. Although minor variations were observed in the mean scores, both groups demonstrated almost similar perceptions and opinion toward e-learning.

Similarly, the comparison between government and private teachers showed no significant difference in their opinions toward e-learning. The calculated *t*-value indicates that teachers from both types of institutions hold comparable views, reflecting a common level of acceptance and awareness of e-learning practices.

Overall, the study concludes that teachers, irrespective of gender and institutional affiliation, share a similar and positive outlook toward e-learning. This suggests that e-learning has gained widespread acceptance among teachers and can be effectively integrated into the education system without the need for differentiated approaches based on gender or type of institution. The findings support the potential for uniform implementation of e-learning initiatives across educational settings.

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